

Flexible and Recyclable Vitrimers for Sustainable Electronic Composites

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Sustainability

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Advanced Composites University of Washington

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23, 101044

Rapid
Manufacturing

Atomistic
Simulations

JPC A 122 (32), 6633-6642

Matter 1 (2), 513-526

Polymer 158, 354-363

Can we enable circular fabrication for electronics composites?

Thermoset | Thermoplastics | Vitrimers

Covalent Adaptable Networks (CANs)

Cross-link Density maintained

Vitrimers: Polymers with Covalent Adaptive Network

Vitrimers enable healing mechanical damage

Key idea: Leverage healing polymers for recyclable composites

Why Soft Vitrimers?

- The rapid growth of **soft electronics** and **robotics**
- The repeated use of soft materials may lead to fatigue damages and failure of part.
- *Opportunity: Soft materials such vitrimer with **conformability** and **stretchability**, **mechanically reliable** and **healability** properties may be useful for these applications*

Synthesis of vitrimer

(a) Step-1: Synthesis of polyester adipate with carboxylic end groups

Step-2: Crosslinking

(b) Schematic for vitrimerization mechanism through transesterification

- ✓ Formation of polyesters with carboxylic end group were confirmed from HNMR and FTIR.
- ✓ The crosslinking process with ester-linkage confirmed.

Thermal properties of vitrimer

✓ Shows good thermal stability

✓ The only T_g value observed indicating no uncrosslinked monomers in the after crosslinking.

Flexibility and healability properties of soft vitrimer

(b) Healing properties at 150°C

✓ The **good healability and weldability** show, the materials are reprocessable and remoldable in nature.

Toughness for flexible vitrimers

(d)

5% strain

10% strain

100% strain

Crack propagation

Crack opening

The resulted vitrimers shows good extension upto 300% with toughness energy 476 J/m^3 compared to the hard vitrimers

Viscoelasticity properties

Thermomechanical analysis

Observed broad peaks indicate, the above the topological freezing temperature T_v , more reversible reactions and show effective flow properties in the matrix.

ReaxFF molecular dynamics simulations of vitrimers

Polymer chain coiling in vitrimers results in higher strain to failures

Applications in Electronic Composites

Fabrication process of cable

Extrusion

Healing Process In Electronic USB Cable

150 °C
→
healing

Electronic USB cable

data transmission

charging

Swelling Experiments for Component Recovery

Swelling polymer Separation of polymer

Supplementary Video 1

Vitrimer swelling
in THF

Summary

- ✓ Inclusion of polymeric thermoplastics with increased chain length into the crosslinked network make them flexible and tough materials.
- ✓ Thermomechanical method can be a good technique to determine the more like topological freezing temperature.
- ✓ The synthesized vitrimer gives good flexible(300% strain) and toughness properties with 476J/m^3
- ✓ The flexible vitrimers can be a good candidate for the other electronics in terms of their fatigue and healability properties.

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